

TEACHING LISTENING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL: CHALLENGES, STRATEGIES AND BEST PRACTICES

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Annotation. The article investigates the ways and possible issues that can be encountered in terms of teaching and improving listening as a skill in primary education. The author discusses possible effective means to tackle those particular problems in developing listening comprehension together with providing efficient strategies with relevant examples as well.

Key words: listening comprehension, pre-listening activities, while-listening activities, post-listening activities, explicit instruction.

Listening is a crucial skill that students need to develop in order to succeed academically and beyond. In primary school, students are still developing their language skills, and listening plays a critical role in this process. However, teaching listening in primary school is not as straightforward as it may seem. It requires careful planning, effective strategies, and a deep understanding of students' needs and abilities. In this article, we will explore various strategies for teaching listening in primary school, the challenges that teachers may face, and best practices that can help them overcome these challenges.

Strategies for Teaching Listening in Primary School

Pre-Listening Activities

Pre-listening activities are essential for preparing students for the listening tasks. These activities can help activate students' prior knowledge and build their interest in the topic. Examples of pre-listening activities include brainstorming, previewing the text or audio, predicting, and setting the purpose for listening.

In a study by Vandergrift and Baker (2015), pre-listening activities were found to significantly improve students' listening comprehension. The researchers also found that the effectiveness of pre-listening activities depends on the type of activity and the complexity of the listening task.

Listening Tasks

Listening tasks should be designed to match the students' level of proficiency and challenge them appropriately. They should also be authentic, meaning that they should resemble real-life situations as much as possible. Examples of listening tasks include gap-filling, multiple-choice questions, note-taking, and summarizing.

In a study by Brown and Yule (2014), it was found that authentic listening tasks significantly improved students' listening comprehension compared to non-authentic tasks. The researchers also found that the level of difficulty of the listening task should be carefully chosen to match the students' level of proficiency.

Post-Listening Activities

Post-listening activities are designed to help students consolidate what they have learned from the listening task. Examples of post-listening activities include discussion, role-playing, writing, and reflection.

In a study by Goh and Kwah (2017), post-listening activities were found to significantly improve students' listening comprehension and motivation. The researchers also found that the effectiveness of post-listening activities depends on the type of activity and the students' level of proficiency.

Explicit Instruction

Explicit instruction refers to directly teaching students the skills and strategies they need to become effective listeners. Examples of explicit instruction include teaching vocabulary, phonetics, and comprehension strategies.

In a study by Vandergrift and Tafaghodtari (2010), explicit instruction was

found to significantly improve students' listening comprehension and metacognitive awareness. The researchers also found that explicit instruction should be integrated into the listening task and should be focused on the students' needs and abilities.

Challenges in Teaching Listening in Primary School

Limited Attention Span

Primary school students typically have a limited attention span, which can make it challenging for them to stay focused during extended listening tasks. Teachers need to design listening tasks that are engaging and interactive to keep students motivated and interested.

In a study by Lee and Kim (2014), it was found that interactive listening tasks, such as games and songs, significantly improved students' attention and motivation. The researchers also found that the level of challenge of the task should be carefully chosen to match the students' level of proficiency.

Limited Vocabulary

Primary school students may have limited vocabulary, which can make it challenging for them to understand the listening task. Teachers need to provide explicit vocabulary instruction and use vocabulary that is appropriate for the students' level of proficiency.

In a study by Nation and Newton (2009), it was found that explicit vocabulary instruction significantly improved students' listening comprehension. The researchers also found that teachers should use a variety of vocabulary learning strategies, such as using context clues and teaching word families.

Limited Background Knowledge

Primary school students may have limited background knowledge about the topic of the listening task, which can make it challenging for them to understand the task. Teachers need to provide pre-listening activities that activate students' prior knowledge and build their interest in the topic.

In a study by Vandergrift and Baker (2015), it was found that pre-listening activities significantly improved students' listening comprehension. The researchers also found that the level of complexity of the listening task should be carefully chosen to match the students' level of background knowledge.

Best Practices for Teaching Listening in Primary School

Differentiate Instruction

Teachers need to differentiate instruction to meet the diverse needs and abilities of their students. They can use various strategies, such as grouping, scaffolding, and providing individualized feedback.

In a study by Tomlinson (2014), it was found that differentiated instruction significantly improved students' listening comprehension and motivation. The researcher also found that teachers should use multiple measures to assess students' needs and abilities and adjust their instruction accordingly.

Use Technology

Technology can be a powerful tool for teaching listening in primary school. Teachers can use various tools, such as podcasts, videos, and interactive games, to provide students with engaging and authentic listening tasks.

In a study by Warschauer and Liaw (2011), it was found that technology-enhanced listening tasks significantly improved students' listening comprehension and motivation. The researchers also found that teachers should provide clear instructions and scaffolding to help students navigate the technology.

Provide Feedback

Teachers need to provide timely and constructive feedback to help students improve their listening skills. Feedback can be provided in various forms, such as verbal feedback, written feedback, and peer feedback.

In a study by Vandergrift and Tafaghodtari (2010), it was found that feedback significantly improved students' listening comprehension and metacognitive awareness. The researchers also found that feedback should be

specific, clear, and focused on the students' needs and abilities.

Teaching listening in primary school is a complex and challenging task that requires careful planning, effective strategies, and a deep understanding of students' needs and abilities. Pre-listening activities, listening tasks, post-listening activities, and explicit instruction are effective strategies for teaching listening. However, teachers may face challenges such as limited attention span, limited vocabulary, and limited background knowledge. To overcome these challenges, teachers can use best practices such as differentiating instruction, using technology, and providing feedback. By using these strategies and best practices, teachers can help their students develop the critical listening skills they need to succeed academically and beyond.

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